

The health inventory of seasoned radiologic technologists in the medical field

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Abstract

The study aims to identify the arising health problems among seasoned radiologic technologists working in the medical field throughout their professional careers. The researchers of the study probed upon three main aspects of the occupational workforce, namely, the working environment, the individual lifestyle, and the exposure to ionizing radiation. An extensive descriptive-qualitative method of informational analysis upon all available related literature from different electronic database has significantly led the researchers to form a conclusive framework of established data conveying that the overall outcomes of the emerging health issues of seasoned radiologic technologists in the latter part of their career such as debilitating musculoskeletal disorders, chronic stress, hospital acquired infections and even elevated incidence of occurring cancer risks to name a few can be directly attributed by cofounding health hazards that are built upon the aspects of the working environment, individual lifestyle, and exposure to ionizing radiation.

Keywords: Seasoned radiologic technologist; Ionizing radiation; Health inventory; Arising health problems.

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Introduction

Health inventory is an assessment tool that can be specifically designed for medical allied professionals. This is a helpful instrument in providing insights into the current health status of an individual, looking for health patterns as well as tendencies and risks associated with the overall factors that are taken into consideration for pulling up an assessment with the information given. The health inventory mainly tackles the different aspects of the general well-being of a person under assessment, which the assessment tool mainly investigates, including the information provided about an individual's lifestyle practices, family background, and past health problems, as well as the inclusion of the holistic well-being (e.g., physiological, emotional, social, and psychological) of an individual, capturing the general outlook of health. Additionally, the health inventory can also be a great instrument to express the different influencing factors that affect the health of an individual from a macro perspective, identifying the current health problems as well as the prediction of health risks in an occupational workforce.

The need for a health inventory in the field of medical allied professionals, such as the field of radiologic technology, plays a vital role in understanding the current health problems of radiologic technologists and being able to identify the rising health risks for practicing the profession. It is because the field of radiologic technology serves as an evolving auxiliary branch of radiology that mainly deals with the utilization of ionizing and non-ionizing radiation to produce diagnostic images of the human body for the determination of different pathological conditions and the treatment of a wide array of diseases.

The usage of both ionizing and non-ionizing radiation sources in the workplace can be considered as one of the main health hazards that radiologic technologists usually face daily, aside from other factors that may exist within the working environment, such as exposure to various patients in a hospital setting, the individual's lifestyle choices, and the holistic well-being of an individual, among others. The researcher's ulterior motive in conducting the study is to assess the current health problems that radiologic technologists are currently facing by identifying the different components that influence the health outcomes of an individual for the purpose of raising awareness among the occupational workforce about their future health outcomes and to serve as a tool for improvement and innovation for a better working environment in the field of radiologic technology. The study focused on analyzing the health status of seasoned radiologic technologists. Particularly, it aims to determine common health problems and risks that are acquired within their years of service, such as working environment, individual lifestyle, and radiation exposure.

Background of the Study

The radiologic technology profession is one of the medical allied professions that continues to advance with the scientific and technological advancements of the modern era. It is one of the youngest allied medical professions to celebrate its 125 years of existence since the discovery of x-rays by Wilhelm Conrad Roentgen on November 8, 1895. The shifting paradigms of the profession marked its growth within the international and local labor markets to continue expanding its horizons in terms of population growth in the medical allied profession that, according to recent data acquired by the researchers from the Board of Radiologic Technology—Professional Regulations Commission (BORT-PRC), a census with a total number of registered radiologic technologists in the Philippine setting is 8,287 from 2014 up to February 21, 2019, excluding the recently concluded Radiologic Technology Licensure Examination (RTLE) on July 28-29, 2019. Alongside these advances and the growing occupational workforce, the field of academic radiologic technology is seemingly behind in terms of scientific literature. These problems of scanty resources within the local research setting with regard to the direct observation and analysis of the health inventory of seasoned radiologic technologists mainly prompted the researchers to bridge the gaps in the published scientific literature with a positive outlook to further strengthen and establish the understanding of the importance of health assessment and its underlying principles to the health outlook of an individual in relation to the field of radiologic technology.

Scope and Limitation

The study mainly revolves around the health inventory of the seasoned radiologic technologists that are working as part of the medical diagnostics team. The study is bound to find existing relationships between the main variables of the study that include the working environment, the individual lifestyle, the family medical history, and the profile of radiation exposure. The study's main limitation is that the researchers were unable to harness a set of raw data and provide statistical interpretations towards the analysis of the findings within the study. Instead, the researchers heavily relied upon the different electronic databases for a wide range of available literature relating to the study and formulated an interpretational analysis of the accumulated literature for the summary of findings and the derivation of the study's conclusions.

The main reason why the researchers were not able to conduct data-gathering procedures within the selected affiliated hospitals is due to the worldwide pandemic, which is the COVID-19 (Coronavirus Disease—2019), putting the affiliated hospitals inaccessible for nonessential personnel and unauthorized visits, making it impossible for the data gathering to commence.

Significance of the Study

The study being conducted by the researchers aims to benefit the following:

- A. **Radiologic Technologists.** The researchers aim to provide insights regarding the current health status of occupational groups, hoping that the outcome of the research paper would bring awareness and educate the radiologic technologists on optimizing one's health.
- B. **Students of BS Radiologic Technology.** The researcher's study outcome may serve as an additional learning tool for the students to better understand and to raise awareness of the underlying health problems that are common within the professional field of radiologic technology.
- C. **Future researchers.** This research may serve as a baseline analysis for an in-depth understanding regarding the health inventory of the seasoned radiologic technologists.

Methodology

Research Design

The researchers of the study employed a combination of a case study—a qualitative and descriptive approach—in determining the important variables in the study and finding their causal relationships with each other (Koh & Owen, 2000). In this research technique, the investigator explores single or multiple bounded systems over time through detailed, in-depth data collection involving multiple sources of information (e.g., observations, interviews, audiovisual material, and documents) and reports a case description and case-based themes mainly describing the macro perspective of a specific phenomenon under study (Harrison et al., 2017). The researchers conducted an informational analysis on the possible variables that mainly influence and shape the total health outcomes of radiologic technologists in the medical field through observation and description of their qualities.

Research Instrument

The research instrument that was utilized by the researcher to harness the primary and secondary data was using different electronic databases such as Google Scholar, Elsevier, PubMed Central, ResearchGate, and other government and non-government organizations published electronic articles related to the general topics of radiation risks, health aspects, lifestyle, and health background. Narrowing the results with the following criteria, the data from the electronic database should be published articles and editorials from peer-reviewed journals. The language format of the selected literatures should be in English, while the date of the published electronic materials should be within the 7-year period range starting from 2013 to 2020.

Research Plan

The researchers of the study identified two main phases in their data-gathering process.

1. Planning and preparation phase, where the researchers brainstormed ideas on how to specifically narrow down the search for the published electronic materials needed for the study's informational analysis.

2. Data gathering phase, where the researchers had employed the ideas and started to examine the wide array of available literature found within the different electronic databases.

Figure 1. Data Gathering Procedure Flowchart

Ethical Considerations

Researchers ensured that the informational analysis and outcomes of the study will be purely based on literature and experiences. The proper acknowledgment of the electronic data gathered within different internet databases will be cited accordingly, and so the researchers will surely maintain the sense of objectivity within the analysis of the study outcomes, therefore eliminating any forms of informational biases within the research paper.

Results and Discussion

The researchers were able to identify and form literature-based evidence about the health inventory of radiologic technologists divided into categories and risk associating its overall outcomes to the arising health problems in the occupational group.

Health Problems Arising from the Working Environment

The researchers' thorough findings and informational analysis with the related literature highly suggest that the health problems arising that radiologic technologists usually encounter can be clustered into three groups.

Physical Health Problem: Work-Related Musculoskeletal Disorders (WRMSDs)

Work-related musculoskeletal disorders (WRMSDs) are a group of physical health problems that emerge because of dealing with the different types of physical injuries and biomechanical stressors that are present in the workplace. These physical health problems typically comprise chronic lower back pain, repetitive strain injuries (RSIs), upper body strain (commonly found in the shoulder, neck, and wrist), as well as general muscular strain, commonly observed in radiologic technologists working in a hospital-based setting.

The researcher's findings suggest that two out of seven of the most common imaging and therapeutic specialties in the field of radiologic technology are prone to developing WRMSDs over a long period of time; due to the intensive physical demands, the imaging modalities need from the radiologic technologists to operate together with an added factor of a large influx of patient volume compared to other imaging and therapeutic modalities, which imaging specialties are general radiography and ultrasonography.

In general radiography, the tremendous amount of physical labor is expected to be sustained by radiographers. These radiologic technologists must face a wide variety of tasks daily that typically revolve around the proper patient positioning during every diagnostic procedure to achieve a desired image, carrying and transferring non-ambulatory patients who suffered from trauma and loss of consciousness for a diagnostic examination, as well as manipulation of heavy imaging equipment around the department for the commencement of different imaging protocols. These daily routines radiographers usually experience during work hours put physical strain and pressure on the body, resulting in musculoskeletal disorders over long periods of time, such as general muscular strain felt within the upper body region specific to the neck and shoulders as well as the development of chronic lower back pain.

Additionally, the researchers found out that ultrasound technologists also experience a specific form of WRMSDs called Repetitive Strain Injury (RSI). It is a term used to describe a gradual process of accumulating damage to nerves, muscles, and tendons caused by repetitive motion and overuse (Hecht, 2017). The researchers identified that occurrences of RSIs within ultrasound technologists commonly take place within the upper body, especially in the wrists, resulting in a health condition called carpal tunnel syndrome, which is the impingement of the median nerve within the carpal canal, giving rise to numerous disabling symptoms such as numbness, pain, and even tingling sensations in radiation within the areas of the hand and wrist. The data suggests that the prevalence of these WRMSDs in ultrasound technologists is usually high for the main reason that the job description entails the usage of scanning probes in performing diagnostic procedures that require a lot of repetitive hand movements and manipulation of ultrasound transducers over a long period of time, making the population susceptible to contracting this form of WRMSDs in their professional careers.

The existence of WRMSDs is generally attributed to three main factors that significantly play a vital role in their development: first is the intensive labor demands, by which radiologic technologists are usually subjected to high amounts of physical stress caused by the demands of the workplace (Werderman, 2020). Those generally acknowledge the radiologic technologists as a group who are responsible for 67% of the total workload done inside the Radiology Department, which is always necessary for exerting a minimal to a maximum amount of upper body strength in performing imaging protocols.

Second is the poor workplace practices, which constitutes a variety of improper biomechanical measures that are performed when executing different imaging protocols such as the improper biomechanics in lifting heavy objects, maintaining incorrect posture while standing and sitting, and strengthening through inappropriate hand grips toward an ultrasound probe which can cause WRMSDs (Ofori-Manteaw et al., 2015). Last is the lack of knowledge of proper ergonomics in the workplace, which serves as a causal factor for why the improper workplace practices exist (Fisher, 2015). It is typically attributed to the lack of ample education on how to deal with the arising physical demands at work with proper ergonomics. This imposes serious health problems in the long run if they are not managed properly.

Psychological Health Problem: Chronic Workplace Stress

A study by Ogenyi et al. (2018) found out that radiologic technologists are among the medical allied professionals that experience chronic job stress as part of their professional careers in a hospital-based work setting. The stress derived from the workplace is a common response that an individual radiologic technologist sustains, which basically arises from experiencing certain stressors that trigger imbalance within a working environment, leading to the occurrence of job stress in the workplace (Di Marco et al., 2016). These psychological manifestations of job stress are usually forsaken since the signs and symptoms of job stress firsthand are not that evident after all. But over a period, the actual accumulation of all the psychological impacts of the job stress towards an individual can cascade into the development of chronic job stress.

According to a study by Wagaman et al. (2015), the chronic and excessive amounts of stress at work typically revealed warning signs and symptoms that usually present themselves as feeling anxious, irritable, and depressed; problems in sleeping; generalized fatigue; apathy (loss of interest at work); trouble concentrating; and even social withdrawal. It suggests that the effects of this debilitating psychological health problem on the radiologic technologists undermine the overall job performance and efficiency of an individual in the workplace, interfering with the normal biologic processes within the human body.

The researchers discovered that the chronic job stress the radiologic technologists commonly experience at work can be attributed to three main factors. First is the overall physical and mental demands the job has to offer towards the occupational workforce. This is due to the practice of the profession, which entails the physical exertion of strength over long periods of time as well as thinking critically to come up with solutions in terms of the arising problems in executing an imaging protocol while staying focused under an extreme amount of pressure. Second is the latter health concern that arises from practicing the profession, which includes the development of stress and anxiety regarding the risks of developing stochastic effects of radiation during and after their practice as professional radiologic technologists. Lastly, there are varying consequences of social interactions in the workplace, such as the perceived social belongingness in the organization as well as the existence of harassment, bullying, and discrimination in the workplace (Elei, 2016).

Hospital Acquired Health Problems: Pulmonary and Blood Borne Infections

Radiology technologists in the workplace are constantly exposed to a wide array of infectious hazards that are present in the hospital-based setting, which the occupational group must deal with daily. The inferential analysis of related literature has identified two common forms of health problems that radiologic technologists harbor from the workplace. The most common form of hospital-acquired pulmonary infection is pulmonary tuberculosis (PTB), a communicable disease that is primarily caused by *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. A preliminary diagnostic examination of this pulmonary infection is commonly referred to the Radiology Department for chest radiography. Inferential analysis of literature suggests that radiologic technologists, together with other medical allied professionals, are most likely to contract this infectious disease. Radiologic technologists must sustain daily exposure from droplet transmission (sneezing and coughing) and direct contact with a patient with either a suspected or active PTB case.

The second most common form of hospital-acquired infectious disease is the bloodborne infection. These are groups of infectious diseases that primarily arise from exposure to infectious body fluids such as blood, cerebrospinal fluid (CSF), mucous membranes, and other bodily fluids that are labeled infectious. Informational analysis from related literature specified three of the most prevalent bloodborne pathogens that radiologic technologists are at risk of developing. These are the two classes of Hepatitis Viral Infection (classes B and C) as well as Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV), which are commonly transmitted through direct bodily fluid contact. It is an inevitable part of the overall diagnostic process that radiologic technologists must perform, ensuring the proper positioning and giving clear instructions to the patients during and after the radiological examination. Lastly is the needle stick injury that a radiologic technologist can accidentally sustain from administering intravenous (IV) contrast media. According to Ogenyi et al. (2018), 37% of the needle stick injuries sustained by radiologic technologists typically result in contracting Hepatitis B viral infection rather than Hepatitis C and HIV infections.

Overall, these debilitating health problems found within the working environment of radiologic technologists are generally caused by the occupational health hazards present within the hospital-based setting, such that these hazards are considered risks that are commonly linked to the working environment, directly translating into a development of health problems as time goes by. These possible health threats identified by the researchers furthermore diverge into two specific points of origin that can either be biologic or non-biologic in nature. A health hazard can be classified as biologic in origin when a health threat basically comes from an individual exposure to biological pathogens present within the working environment, causing health problems in an employee. But when a health threat arises from a variety of physical, psychological, or social problems an individual receives from the working environment, it is already considered non-biologic in nature.

Health Problems Arising from the Individual Lifestyle

Lifestyle is a way used by an individual or group of people sharing a common system of belief in terms of characteristics that are based on behaviors, activities, and diet that greatly influence the quality of life. According to a study by Farhud (2015), 60% of the quality of the life of an individual will have on a lifetime solely depends on his/her individual lifestyle choices. The inferential analysis suggests that lifestyle alone can be considered as one of the defining factors that can directly influence the overall health of an individual as well as a predictive tool for the assessment of the arising of health problems that could possibly dictate an individual's survival and longevity. This establishment of the direct causal relationship between lifestyle and arising health problems found within radiologic technologists can be directly attributed to the shifting paradigms of the modern era on how they are living for a specific kind of lifestyle for which it can either be classified as healthy or unhealthy. Lifestyle shifts and practices are the key predisposing factors in how lifestyle can be a great threat to one's health and be a great source of benefit. On the other hand, these fluctuations brought by lifestyle events in an individual can be attributed to the existence of the nine key health factors (Farhud, 2015) and the modifiable and non-modifiable risk factors (Tabish, 2017) in the instability of an individual lifestyle.

The identification of the Nine Key Health Factors was proposed by Farhud in 2015 regarding the impacts of lifestyle on health, which mainly comprises the following: first is the diet and body mass index (BMI); the healthy food choices that an individual makes certainly determine how well the outcome of the body mass index would be. The inferential analysis of the researchers suggests that the unhealthy or poor diet of an individual primarily consists of consuming the extreme highs and lows of sugar, salt, unsaturated fat, and carbohydrates, which can certainly result in an unhealthy score in BMI, leading to either obesity or malnutrition.

A meta-analytic study by Rizzuto and Fratiglioni (2014) found that there is an established correlation between obesity and the development of cardiovascular disorders as well as cancer developments in the colon, kidneys, and endometrium of an obese individual, and as for malnutrition, the study found out that there is a positive correlation between a decreased body mass index and a susceptibility to harboring acute or chronic infections. Second is exercise (physical activity), which operates as a positive mediating barrier for an individual in developing acute or chronic diseases that are commonly linked to a predictive tool of longevity in an individual. Third is the amount of sleep, which suggests that sleep plays a vital role in keeping the physical and mental health of an individual aligned in a way that sleep functions as a restorative process on the body's natural homeostasis that promotes healing. Fourth is sexual behavior that stands as a physiologic need for an individual in a way that should be in a healthy point of view; risky and dysfunctional sexual behaviors are commonly linked to developing sexually transmitted infections. Fifth is substance abuse, which mainly constitutes alcoholic abuse and chronic smoking addiction. Informational analysis of the literature has pointed out that smoking alone is attributed to five million deaths annually (Rizzuto & Fratiglioni, 2014), causing a cluster of health problems like cardiovascular diseases, chronic obstructive pulmonary diseases (COPD), and lung cancer. Additionally, the large intake of alcoholic substances can also elevate the risks of cardiovascular diseases and liver and kidney problems.

Sixth is the medication abuse that typically translates into the improper use of medicines for different kinds of illnesses without prior consultation with a physician that imposes a threat of yielding more harm than benefit from the medications. Seventh is the application of modern technologies, which can be both beneficial and harmful at the same time. The use of technological advancements has been significantly improving the daily lives of individuals, but the excessive and uncontrolled use of these technological advancements, like cellular devices and computers, can lead to addiction. Eight is recreation or leisure time. It has been confirmed that recreation significantly decreases the mortality rate of an individual by positively stimulating the psychosocial and physiologic process. Lastly, studying, which is considered the art of learning, helps people to become more aware as individuals that serve a primary function to nurture physical and mental health better.

Aside from the Nine Key Factors of Lifestyle by Farhud (2015), the researchers also considered the two types of risk factors that were specified by Tabish (2017) in developing lifestyle diseases, which mainly comprise the modifiable and non-modifiable risk factors that equally play a significant impact on the development of lifestyle health problems with the Nine Key Health Factors. The informational analysis of modifiable risk factors suggests that the lifestyle behavior of an individual can be remodeled over time, consisting of alcohol abuse, chronic smoking, unhealthy diet, and sedentary physical state, which can specifically fluctuate at different paces. While the non-modifiable risk factors mainly comprise varying variables that cannot be changed and are deemed constant, which an individual has no control over, including genetics, age, sex, and the overall environment surrounding an individual. Overall, the abovementioned factors shifting indefinitely over time can emerge as a health problem.

The researcher's informational analysis of related literature leads to the study of a list of the four most common clusters of health problems that may arise due to an individual's lifestyle, which comprises:

Cardiovascular Disorders (CVDs) are clusters of health problems that specifically ravage the heart and the blood vessels in the body, manifesting into coronary heart disease, cerebrovascular disease, and peripheral arterial disease, to mention a few. CVDs are responsible for 80% of deaths on a global scale, as well as 85% of causes of disabilities in an individual, making a risk factor of chronic smoking, high blood pressure, high cholesterol, diabetes, and unhealthy diet (Goyal & Yusuf, 2006, as cited by Senapati et al., 2015).

Diabetes mellitus is a metabolic disorder that basically interferes with the sugar uptake in the human body. This is the most prevalent metabolic disorder affecting a wide age bracket, starting from children up to adults. Additionally, diabetes mellitus is classified into two types, which are Type 1 Diabetes Mellitus (insulin-dependent type), commonly observed in youth, children, and adults, which means the inability to produce their own supply of insulin in the body; while Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (non-insulin-dependent type) is more prevalent in adults, commonly influenced by unhealthy food-eating habits and lifestyle, with a mechanism of insulin tolerance inside the body (Pang & Gu, 2004).

Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disorders (COPD) are groups of chronic pulmonary inflammatory diseases that cause an obstruction of airflow in the lungs, which takes form in chronic bronchitis and emphysema. It has been known that the causal agent for this health problem is smoking, persistent exposure to common lung irritants such as pollen, and polluted and suspended particles in the air (Cipolla et al., 2018).

Cancer is characterized by abnormal cellular growth in a specific part of the human body. According to Tabish (2017), five types of cancer are commonly identified to be attributed to an individual's lifestyle, which includes cervical, lung, breast, prostate, and colorectal cancer. The development of these types of cancer can be attributed to an unhealthy diet in conjunction with a physically sedentary lifestyle as well as the risk-modifying behaviors of chronic tobacco smoking and heavy alcohol drinking.

Health Problems and Risks associated with Radiation Exposure

The exposure of medical radiation workers to ionizing radiation in the occupational setting is one of the inevitable scenarios that occurs daily in line duty that puts the radiologic technologists at a certain disadvantage for the main reason that receiving chronic exposures to low levels of ionizing radiation has an established biologic effect. Literature analysis has identified that being able to classify a chronic low-level dosage of ionizing radiation in the occupational setting shall satisfy two main conditions: first, a medical radiation worker must be continuously subjected to receiving small doses of ionizing radiation over a long period of time, and second, the total accumulated occupational dosage should not exceed the 100 mSv (millisievert) mark (Mourad, 2019). It was delineated by the International Commission on Radiation Protection (ICRP)'s guidelines that the occupational dosage of radiologic technologists should not surpass the 20 mSv/year limit for an average of 100 mSv in five years of continuous low dosage exposure to satisfy the conditions under the chronic low-level exposure (ICRP, 2020).

The accumulation of the low dosages of ionizing radiation is basically attributed to the utilization of both ionizing and non-ionizing radiation in imaging and therapeutic modalities of radiology, creating a variety of potential hazards in human health (Committee to Assess Health Risks from Exposure to Low Levels of Ionizing Radiation, 2006). The elucidation of this occurring phenomenon and its association with emerging health problems in professions are anchored in the two evidence-based principles that govern the outcomes of chronic low-level exposure to ionizing radiation. First is the stochastic effects of ionizing radiation (later effect). Informational analysis of literature states a mechanism of biologic damage in a living organism that is particularly derived from low levels of exposure to ionizing radiation, which has a specific unfavorable biologic response that usually appears later within a span of months, years, or even within a lifetime of an exposed individual. The unique mechanism of this biologic damage to the human body mainly relies on the probability or chance for which it does not follow any thresholds to what extent an organism can be irradiated to produce a response but rather any amount of exposure from ionizing radiation, as long as it is less than 100 mSv, is expected to cause a detrimental response that is statistically based on estimated risks that may develop over a lifetime, such as solid and malignant cancers in organ-specific sites, leukemia, and genetic effects (mutations).

The second principle is the Linear Non-Threshold Model. It is a mathematical model used to describe an established relationship between corresponding radiation levels and their respective biological responses. The LNT model basically works hand in hand with the stochastic effects of ionizing radiation, having a core principle that relies on the probability or chance that is expressed in a linear function allowing continuous increments of doses as long as the organism is constantly irradiated by low levels of ionizing radiation, which implies that lower dose exposure yields a decreased probability of developing a response while elevated dose exposures can lead to an increased chance of developing a biologic response (Tran & Seeram, 2017). This implies that the LNT model follows a non-threshold dose limit, suggesting that even the lowest exposure to ionizing radiation bears an unfavorable biologic response, with an absolute lowest value dosage that could theoretically reach zero. The stochastic effects of protracted low dosages of ionizing radiation are known to be associated with late development of carcinogenic health problems and even elevated risks (Lee et al., 2018).

The informational analysis of literature pointed out two main themes about the effects of protracted low doses of ionizing radiation in the human body. First, low chronic dosages of ionizing radiation can elevate the risks of developing carcinogenic disease. Second, the exposure to ionizing radiation at low levels can be positively correlated with the development of different types of cancers, excluding other environmental factors. This idea was proven by an observational study of Wang et al. (2016). It is by this that the researchers have clearly identified the incidence of cancer via the follow-up survey within a group of medical radiation workers in China from 1950 to 2011. It has been identified that malignant growth of tumors (solid type of cancer) was found to be prevalent among the occupational group, which includes lungs, liver, stomach, colon, and pancreatic cancers, together with the additional findings of the occurrence of breast cancer and leukemia among medical radiation workers.

The inferential analysis proposes that the overall accumulated biological damage derived from the low-level exposure to ionizing radiation over time cascades into a development of serious health problems in such a way that the biologic responses of a living organism being irradiated can no longer adapt to the continuous challenges of ionization, suggesting that ionizing radiation can be considered as one of the carcinogenic factors that is naturally occurring within the environment (Vaiserman et al., 2017).

Figure 2. Research paradigm

The concept map illustrated above in Figure 2 demonstrates the main sources of health problems of seasoned radiologic technologists, shaping the occupational group's health outcomes and overall well-being.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The researchers of the study aimed to qualitatively describe the arising health problems that the seasoned radiologic technologists are experiencing. The data gathering procedures of the study heavily relied upon the use of wide variety of electronic databases such as Google Scholar, PubMed Central, Elsevier, and ResearchGate for harnessing different related literatures that are used in the study. It was because the researchers were not able to conduct proper data gathering procedures because of the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic. Although, the researchers were able to produce a reliable framework of data that was sourced and formed through the exhaustion of informational analysis coming from different related literatures as well as the inclusion of the investigators' inferential analysis which was objectively based on the arising health problems of seasoned radiologic technologists to diminish subjective biases in the study.

Researchers have identified that the common arising health problems found within seasoned radiologic technologists can be attributed into three main variables of the study: First is the working environment which has a significant contribution to the arising health problems among seasoned radiologic technologists that it manifests itself into acquiring physical, psychological and even biological health problems. Second is the individual lifestyle that has been found to have a positive correlation with the development of health problems and trigger fluctuations in human health. Lastly is the radiation exposure that plays a significant role in the identification of the elevated risks in cancer development as well as the prediction of cancer incidence.

The arising health problems of the seasoned radiologic technologists can be gauged through their working environment, individual lifestyle, and exposure to radiation suggesting that the overall health outcomes of the occupational group solely rely upon the interaction towards the extrinsic and intrinsic factors. The arising health problems of seasoned radiologic technologists can be positively correlated with two or more cofounding factors that can be derived from the three main variables of the study. The Radiologic Technology profession is considerably "hazardous" for all the imposed health threats existing within the professional practice making them one of the vulnerable groups among the medical allied professionals working in the health care industry.

Future researchers should conduct qualitative and quantitative assessments with the use of a survey tool regarding the arising health problems of seasoned radiologic technologists for the formation of a conclusive data analysis based on statistical information, to individually assess and explore the different health problems in specialized areas of imaging and therapeutic modalities in the field of radiologic technology. Expanded coverage in terms of age and years of experience shall be studied to properly gauge the significant differences that can be found in working radiologic technologists. The improvement of knowledge and awareness towards the self-optimization of health and its outcomes makes it easier to provide a much safer working environment for the radiologic technologists.

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